

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS OF NEW ADAMANTANE DERIVATIVES OF PYRAZOLO[3,4-d]PYRIMIDINE AS POTENTIAL ANTICANCER DRUGS

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Abstract

Four new pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines (4)–(7) were successfully synthesized in good yields by reacting 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-4-ol with various alkylating agents (methyl iodide, tert-benzyl bromide, benzyl chloride,) at room temperature in DMF using liquid-solid phase transfer catalysis. The structures of (4)–(7) were proven by NMR spectroscopy. The anticancer activities of (4)–(7) against human colorectal carcinoma (HCT 116), human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2), and human breast cancer (MCF-7) cell lines, as well as one normal cell line (WI38) were investigated using MTT assay and sunitinib as a reference. Compounds (4) and (5) exhibited anticancer activity comparable to the reference drug against all tested cells, with an IC₅₀ range of 22.7–40.75 μM. Both compounds also demonstrated high selectivity indices and minimal cytotoxic effects on normal cell lines.

Keywords: pyrazolopyrimidines, adamantane,, anticancer activity, alkylating agents

Introduction

Cancer is the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular disease. Recent studies have revealed the mechanisms by which normal cells become cancerous [1].

Heterocyclic compounds are a key component of anticancer drugs. In recent years, there has been increased interest in the chemistry of pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines due to their broad biological activities, such as anticancer [2], antibacterial [3], antituberculosis [4], and antitumor [5] activities.

The pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine core is a class of heterocyclic compounds of interest from both a chemical and pharmaceutical perspective, as they have been found to exhibit antitumor activity by inhibiting various types of enzymes, such as Bruton tyrosine kinase (BTK) [6], Src tyrosine kinase [7,8], Myt1 kinase [9], and TRAP1 kinase [10]. The first identified pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine kinase inhibitors were 4-amino-5-(4-methylphenyl)-7-(t-butyl)pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimi-

dine (**A**) and 4-amino-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-7-(t-butyl)pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine (**B**) (Figure 1), which were first discovered as inhibitors of the SRC family of non-receptor tyrosine kinases [11]. Indeed, pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines have multiple active sites, which imparts them with high reactivity, making these heterocycles excellent precursors in the synthesis of new heterocyclic systems that are likely to exhibit a broad spectrum of activity. For example, allopurinol (Figure 1) is used clinically as a drug for the treatment of gout [12]. Accordingly, the synthesis of new pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines has attracted more attention using various synthetic methods [13–17]. On the other hand, it is known that the presence of bulky framework substituents (adamantyl, diamantyl, etc.) in a molecule with pharmacophore groups increases lipophilicity, reduces toxicity, and in some cases significantly enhances the activity of drugs [18–19]. Therefore, it seemed interesting to synthesize pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine derivatives containing the adamantyl fragment.

Figure 1. Chemical structures of known pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine derivatives.

In view of the importance that pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine derivatives have brought to the biological and therapeutic fields, and in continuation of the studies of other authors reported in [20,21], this work reports the synthesis of new pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines (5-7), which have various groups at position 1 of the pyrazolopyrimidine nucleus and an adamantyl moiety at position 4 of the phenyl nucleus. Their structures were confirmed by NMR spectroscopy data. Additional studies of these molecules included in vitro anticancer studies.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis

Scheme 1. Synthesis of compounds (5) – (7).

Materials and methods

All chemicals used in this work were purchased from commercial sources (Sigma-Aldrich, Fluka, St. Louis, MO, USA, and Bio-Parma, United Kingdom). They were used without further purification. Melting points were determined using a Mel-Temp 3.0 apparatus. NMR spectra were obtained using a Bruker Advance/DPX 250 spectrometer (250 MHz ^1H , 62.9 MHz ^{13}C).

Pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidine derivatives (5–7) were synthesized following the procedure outlined in Scheme 1. 2-(1-Ethoxyethylidene)malononitrile (1) and 1-[4-(1-adamantyl)phenyl]hydrazine, isolated from the hydrochloride using the standard procedure, were refluxed in ethanol for 6 h to afford 5-amino-3-methyl-1-phenyl(4-adamantyl)-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile (3). The procedure described in [22] was used as a basis. The latter was reacted with formic acid at reflux for 10 h to obtain compound (4) in 78% yield, which was reacted with the selected alkylating agent: methyl iodide, tert-benzyl bromide, benzyl chloride, to obtain the final products (5), (6) and (7), in 83, 66 and 74% yields, respectively.

3-Methyl-1-phenyl(4-adamantyl)-1,5-dihydro-4H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-4-ol(4).

A solution of 5-amino-3-methyl-1-phenyl(4-adamantyl)-1H-pyrazole-4-carbonitrile (3) (1.0 g, 5.04 mmol) in formic acid (30 mL) was refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice water. The resulting precipitate was filtered off, dried, and recrystallized from ethanol (Scheme 1). Yield 83%. M.p. 153–155 °C. ^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 12.34 (s, 1H), 8.13 (s, 1H), 8.03–8.01 (m, 2H), 7.54–7.50 (m,

2H), 2.52 (s, 3H), 1.02-1.5 (m, 15H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 157.99, 152.24, 148.88, 145.93, 138.29, 129.11, 126.62, 121.36, 105.74, 31.50, 25.20, 16.10, 13.37.

General procedure for the synthesis of compounds (5)-(7).

A solution of DMF (5 mL) containing (4) (0.1 g, 0.44 mmol), K₂CO₃ (1.2 equiv), and tetra-n-butylammonium bromide (TBAB) catalyst was stirred for 35 min. The chosen alkylating agent (1.2 equiv) was then added to the solution, and the mixture was stirred overnight. The mixture was then poured into ice water, and the resulting precipitate was filtered, dried, and recrystallized from ethanol to yield the final product (Scheme 1).

3,5-Dimethyl-1-phenyl(4-adamantyl)-1,5-dihydro-4H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-4-one (5).

Yield 83%. M.p. 163–165 °C. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 8.02–7.99 (m, 2H), 7.54–7.50 (m, 2H), 3.47 (s, 3H), 2.52 (s, 3H), 1.02–1.5 (m, 15H). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 157.60, 151.90, 151.70, 145.86, 138.27, 129.24, 126.66, 121.20, 104.94, 33.15, 31.62, 25.37, 16.21, 13.41.

5-tert-Butyl-3-methyl-1-phenyl(4-adamantyl)-5-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)-1,5-dihydro-4H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-4-one (6)

Scheme 2. Tautomerism of compound (4).

Anticancer Activity

The anticancer activity of compounds (4)–(7) was assessed using a standard MTT assay and sunitinib (a well-known FDA-approved multikinase inhibitor) as a reference against HCT 116, HepG2, and MCF-7 cell lines and the normal WI38 cell line. Compounds (6) and (7) exhibited very weak anticancer activity with IC₅₀ values greater than 67 μM (Table 1). They demonstrate greater cytotoxicity against the normal cell

Yield 66%. M.p. 183–185 °C. ¹H NMR (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 8.02–7.99(m, 2H), 7.54 (m, 2H), 7.13 (m, 1H), 2.55 (s, 3H), 0.86 (s, 9H), 1.02-1.5 (m, 15H). ¹³C NMR (63 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 156.31, 155.3, 151.44, 150.71, 146.10, 138.02, 129.21, 126.87, 121.47, 104.84, 78.65, 75.75, 34.63, 31.68, 27.91, 25.32, 16.11, 13.34.

3-Methyl-5-benzyl-1-phenyl(4-adamantyl)-1,5-dihydro-4H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-4-one (7).

Yield 74%. M.p. 191-192 °C. ¹H NMR (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 8.54 (s, 1H), 8.43 (s, 1H), 8.12–8.03 (m, 4H), 8.12–7.89 (m, 2H), 7.54–7.50 (m, 2H), 4.82 (d, J = 2.5 Hz, 2H), 2.53 (s, 3H), 1.02-1.5 (m, 15H). ¹³C NMR (63 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 192.84, 156.91, 151.84, 146.07, 138.12, 134.27, 129.23, 126.82, 121.44, 51.48, 31.71, 27.91, 25.32, 16.11, 13.32.

Possible tautomeric forms of compound (4) are shown in Scheme 2. The compound has three reactive centers with respect to alkylating agents N5, N7, and O in OH at C4. Alkylation reactions carried out under phase-transfer catalysis conditions lead in each case to only one alkylated product, (5) – (7), showing that N5 of pyrazolopyrimidine is the most reactive center of compound (4).

line than against cancer cell lines. In contrast, (4) and (5) demonstrated anticancer activity comparable to that of the reference standard anticancer drug against cancer cell lines, as they exhibit a three-fold difference compared to sunitinib (IC₅₀ values of 22.7–40.75 μM). Compounds (4) and (5) showed excellent selectivity indices since they exhibited very weak cytotoxic effects on the normal cell line.

Table 1.

In vitro anticancer activity (4)–(7) against HCT 116, HepG2, and MCF-7 cancer cell lines, and the normal WI38 cell line.

Compjund	In Vitro Cytotoxicity IC ₅₀ (μM)				Selectivity Index
	HCT 116	HepG2	MCF-7	WI38	
(4)	33.85	26.56	42.49	>100	0.39
(5)	45.26	37.36	47.68	>100	0.43
(6)	>100	>100	99.64	61.41	1.95
(7)	>100	78.17	>100	51.52	2.29
Sunitinib	20.95	9.80	28.15	65.09	0.35

Conclusions

1. Four new pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidines (4)–(7) were synthesized. Their structures were determined using NMR spectroscopy.

2. The anticancer activity of (4)–(7) is weak compared to the anticancer activity of a reference standard anticancer drug against cancer cells, with an IC₅₀ of 22.7–40.75 μM.

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